

Comparison of Antibiotic Sensitivity of Pattern *Candida albicans* and *Candida parapsilosis* Isolated From Clinical Samples In Intensive Care Unit

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Abstract

A retrospective analysis of the widely used antibiotics all susceptibility testing results from *Candida* (*C.*) *albicans* and *Candida* (*C.*) *parapsilosis* cultured from clinical specimens private hospital (2014-2018) was performed. The VITEK 2 Compact automated microbiology system (bioMérieux) is designed for automated rapid antimicrobial susceptibility testing and identification of clinically relevant *Candida* isolates. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) results previously obtained in recent clinical isolates with well-defined in isolates with well-characterized resistance mechanisms with the microdilution method were re-interpreted for the susceptible, intermediate and resistant categories using the 2018 EUCAST breakpoints. Clinical samples are most commonly isolated from blood, wound and urine samples. In our study, Vorikanozol and Flucytosine showed 100% sensitivity rate both *C. albicans* and *C. parapsilosis*. MAR index value showed only one sample, 0.33 both *C. albicans* and *C. parapsilosis*. Considering the antibiogram, Vorikanozol and Flucytosine should be preferred drugs for both *C. albicans* and *C. parapsilosis* infection isolated from clinical samples.

Keywords: *C. albicans*, *C. parapsilosis*, antibiotic, sensitivity, clinical specimens, intensive care unit

INTRODUCTION

Candida is a dimorphic fungal pathogen that colonizes the mucosal surfaces of approximately 30% of healthy individuals at any given moment [1]. In immunocompetent hosts, the colonization by *Candida* does not cause disease, but during a breach of the anatomical barriers or in immunocompromised hosts, important clinical consequences may ensue. The spectrum of clinical diseases caused by *Candida* spp. comprises clinical syndromes ranging from mucocutaneous infections of the oral and vaginal mucosae to candidemia and deep-seated infections that are often associated with a septic syndrome [2-4]. Although *C. albicans* is still the most prevalent species causing infection, the recent years have witnessed a trend towards an increased prevalence of non-*C. albicans* *Candida* species such as *C. glabrata* *C. krusei* and *C. parapsilosis* [5,6].

C. parapsilosis is a normal human commensal, which is often isolated from hand skin. Intact human skin limits the pathogenicity of *C. parapsilosis*. It is notorious for its affinity for catheter or prosthetic materials, capacity for forming biofilm and ability to grow in hyperalimentation solution [7]. A study in Spain revealed that the risk factors of *C. parapsilosis* infection include vascular catheterization, previous antibiotics history, previous immunosuppressive therapy, malignancy, transplant receipt, neutropenia, and previous colonization [8].

The aim of this study was to determine the characteristics and patterns of antibiotic resistance among isolates of *Candida albicans* and *C. parapsilosis* recovered from clinical specimens in Giresun province.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Candida isolates

Ethical approval is were taken before study. Because of the retrospective analysis, we did not patient approval. 28 *C. albicans* and 59 *C. parapsilosis* were isolated from clinical specimens from the intensive care

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unit of internal medicine in a private hospital. *Candida* isolates were identified to level of species and subspecies by using the morphological and traditional biochemical tests and automatic diagnostic systems currently present in the market and commonly used for YST (21343) in clinical laboratories will therefore have to incorporate these criteria in their instruments to meet the needs of European microbiology laboratories according to standard methods described by [9-11]. All isolates were obtained from patients in intensive care units. In total, 28 *C.albicans* and 59 *C.parapsilosis* were isolated from various clinical samples and detected by the VITEK 2 (bioMérieux) at the microbiology laboratory of our hospital between from January in 2014 to December in 2018. The VITEK 2 Compact Automated Microbiology System (bioMérieux) is designed for the rapid fungal identification at the species level and determination of YST of clinically significant human fungal pathogens [12].

Antibiogram profile of *C.albicans* and *C.parapsilosis*

Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) results previously obtained in recent clinical isolates with well-defined in isolates with well-characterized resistance mechanisms with microdilution method were re-interpreted for the susceptible, intermediate and resistant categories using the 2018 EUCAST breakpoints. Six different antibiotics were used. Antibiotics tested in AST-YS07 (bioMérieux) card included Voriconazole, Flucytosine, Micafungin, Caspofungin, Amphotericin B and Fluconazole.

Multiple Antibiotic Resistance (MAR) indexes

For all isolates, we calculated the MAR index values (a/b, where a represents the number of antibiotics the isolate was resistant to, b represents the total number of antibiotics the isolate tested against). A MAR index value ≥ 0.2 is observed when isolates are exposed to high risk sources of human or animal contamination, where antibiotics use is common; in contrast, a MAR index value ≤ 0.2 observed when antibiotics are seldom or never used [13,14].

RESULTS

The results of the resistance pattern of *Candida albicans*, *C.parapsilosis* isolates in our locality to antimicrobial agents showed that the 28 *Candida albicans*, 59 *Candida parapsilosis* strains tested against six antimicrobial agents in Table 1.

In our study, Voriconazole and Flucytosine showed 100% sensitivity rate both *Candida albicans* and *Candida parapsilosis* and as is illustrated in Table 1. Table 2 shows the antimicrobial susceptibility of all *C.albicans* and *C. parapsilosis* isolated from urine, blood, and wound. MAR index value showed only one sample, 0.33 both *C.albicans* and *C.parapsilosis*. MAR index value of other samples showed 0 both *C.albicans* and *C.parapsilosis*.

Table 1- Antibiotic resistance pattern of 28 *Candida albicans* and 59 *Candida parapsilosis* isolated from clinical specimens in intensive care unit.

Antibiotics	<i>Candida albicans</i>			<i>Candida parapsilosis</i>		
	S	I	R	S	I	R
Voriconazole	28(100%)	-	-	59(100%)	-	-
Flucytosine	28(100%)	-	-	59(100%)	-	-
Micafungin	28(100%)	-	-	5(8%)	54(92%)	-
Caspofungin	28(100%)	-	-	57(97%)	2(3%)	-
Amphotericin B	27(96%)	-	1(4%)	57(97%)	1(1,7%)	1(1,7%)
Fluconazole	27(96%)	-	1(4%)	58(98,3%)	-	1(1,7%)

Table 2: Distribution of 87 *Candida* clinical samples, Sexuality, source, MAR Index and ESBL Producers

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Name of Clinic	<i>Candida albicans</i>			Name of Clinic	<i>Candida parapsilosis</i>		
	Number of samples and source	Sexuality F/M	MAR Index		Number of samples	Sexuality F/M	MAR Index
Anesthesia and Reanimation	19 Blood 2Wound	10M/11F	0(2isl)	Anesthesia and Reanimation	45 Blood	21M/24F	0(44isl); 0,33(1isl)
Internal medicine	1 Blood	1F	0(1isl)	Cardiologia	3 Blood	2M/1B	0(1isl)
Infectious Diseases	2Urine, 1Blood	3M	0,33(1isl) 0(2isl)	Chest Diseases	1 Blood	1M	0(1isl)
Child Health and Diseases	1 Blood	1F	0(1isl)	Child Health and Diseases	7 Blood	4M/3F	0(7isl)
Chest Diseases	1 Blood	1F	0(1isl)	Orthopedics and Travmatology	1 Blood	1M	0(1isl)
Norologia	1 Blood	1M	0(1isl)	Physical therapy and Rehabilitation	1 Blood	1M	0(1isl)

MAR, Multiple Antibiotic Resistance Index, isl; isolates, F; Female, M; Male

DISCUSSION

In our study, when we compared to the sensitivity of Voriconazole, *C.albicans* and *C.parapsilosis* isolates showed high antibiotic sensitivity with 100% Voriconazole. Some researchers have reported a sensitivity rate Voriconazole to *C.albicans* and *C.parapsilosis* in clinical samples [15].

In our study, when we compared to the sensitivity of Flucytosine, *C.albicans* and *C.parapsilosis* isolates showed high antibiotic sensitivity with 100% Flucytosine. Some researchers have reported a sensitivity rate Flucytosine to *C.albicans* and *C.parapsilosis* in clinical samples [16-18]. Our results were similar to Cıkman et al (2014) who also reported that the sensitivity rate of Flucytosine of 100% to *C.albicans* [19].

In our study, when we compared to the sensitivity of Micafungin, *C.albicans* and *C.parapsilosis* isolates showed high antibiotic sensitivity with 100% and 8% Micafungin respectively. Micafungin inhibits the synthesis of 1,3- β -D-glucan, an essential molecule of many pathogenic fungi wall architecture, and exhibits an excellent activity against a great number of *Candida* species many resistant to azoles [20]. Thus, micafungin is a very useful drug for the first line therapy of invasive candidiasis [21].

In our study, when we compared to the sensitivity of Caspofungin, *C.albicans* and *C.parapsilosis* isolates showed high antibiotic sensitivity with 100% and 97% Caspofungin respectively. Some researchers have reported a sensitivity rate Caspofungin to *C.albicans* and *C.parapsilosis* in clinical samples [15].

In our study, when we compared to the sensitivity of Amphotericin B, *C.albicans* and *C.parapsilosis* isolates showed high antibiotic sensitivity with 96% and 97% Amphotericin B respectively. Some researchers have reported a sensitivity rate of Amphotericin B to *C.albicans* and *C.parapsilosis* in clinical samples [15].

In our study, when we compared to the sensitivity of Fluconazole, *C.albicans* and *C.parapsilosis* isolates showed high antibiotic sensitivity with 96% and 98,3% Fluconazole respectively. Some researchers have reported a sensitivity rate Fluconazole to *C.albicans* and *C.parapsilosis* in clinical samples [15,19,22].

CONCLUSION

Considering the antibiogram, Vorikanazol and Flucytosine should be preferred drugs for both *C.albicans* and *C.parapsilosis* infection isolated from clinical samples.

FOOTNOTES

Authors' Contribution: T. C. and D. K. designed and conducted the study. A. A. G. coordinated and performed all the laboratory analyses. T. C. and D. K. analyzed and interpreted all of the data. T. C. and D. K. wrote the first draft of the paper. All authors read, commented on and approved the final manuscript.

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